

Impact Of Competency Developing Interventional Package on Assertive Behavior and Self Esteem Among Children Residing in Selected Orphanages of Bagalkot District

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ABSTRACT

An evaluative study was conducted by using time series design, to assess the impact of competency developing interventional package (CDIP) on Assertive behavior and self esteem among children residing in selected orphanages of Bagalkot District. The researcher used pretest post test control group time series design. The results of the study have shown that Pre test mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior scores of children in both experimental and control group. The pre test mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior scores in experimental group was 79.77 ± 17.076 and 78.10 ± 16.780 in control group, the post test I mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior was 83.77 ± 16.524 where as in control group 78.07 ± 14.661 , Post test II experimental group 86.18 ± 16.411 and control group 78.91 ± 17.287 . In this present study pre test mean scores and SD of self esteem scores in experimental group was 17.74 ± 2.347 and 14.52 ± 2.194 in control group, The present study findings revealed that there is an impact of competency developing interventional package on assertive behavior and self esteem among children under residential care settings.

Keywords: Competency developing interventional package (CDIP), Assertive behavior, self esteem, Orphans and orphanage.

INTRODUCTION

According to various reports citing UNICEF data from around 2021-2022, India had over 29 to 30 million orphaned and abandoned children, representing about 4% of the total child population at the time.¹ According to various reports citing UNICEF data around 2021-2022, India has an estimated 29.6 to 31 million orphaned and abandoned children, representing approximately 4% of the child population. A significant portion of these children are girls due to cultural factors like dowry costs, and only a small fraction, less than 5 lakh, are in institutional care.² Adolescence residing in orphanages are facing with psycho social problems like anxiety, depression, and low self esteem and assertive behavior due to lack of parental support and guidance.³

NEED FOR STUDY

Adolescence is a crucial stage of development where the individuals undergo lot of physical, psychological and social changes and finds it difficult to overcome this stage. The orphan adolescents finds it much more difficult to cross this development stage as they lack support and care from their parents and significant others in the family. Hence it becomes essential for the orphan adolescents to acquire life skills, assertive behavior and self esteem to enhance their psychosocial competence, to make right decision at the right time, sharpen their creative and critical thinking, strengthen their problem solving skill, develop interpersonal relationship skill and enable them to manage their stress and emotions efficiently and promote positive growth and development towards life.⁴

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

A study was conducted to assess the emotional competences among adolescents in Sialkot, Pakistan to evaluate the effectiveness of assertive training intervention to develop and improve social skills. The researcher used quasi- experimental design (pre-test – post-test with control test) was adopted. Simple random sampling technique was adopted. A sample of 40 adolescents was obtained and was further divided into two groups: experimental group was comprised of 20 participants (girls= 10, boys= 10) and control group with the same number. A demographic sheet and Social- Emotional Competence Questionnaire (SECQ) were used for data collection. The experimental group attended assertive training while the control group did not receive treatment. Paired sample t-test showed statistically significant difference in means of overall score of SEC before and after treatment ($t = -15.50$, $p = .000$). Moreover, the pre-post difference on the level of dimensions of social emotional competence was highly significant (pairwise t-tests; all $p < .05$) in the intervention group except on the dimension of decision making with ($t = 1.67$, $p = .110$). The findings of the experiment concluded that assertive training significantly improved the overall social emotional competencies among adolescents.⁵

An evaluative study was conducted on effectiveness of life skill training on self-esteem and self-perception among street children in Kolkata, India. Previous research found the effect of life skill training on gender. Therefore, data were collected from 20 adolescents (12 girls and 8 boys) with an age range of 11–17 years. A purposive sampling technique was followed. The life skill training programme was conducted on 16 sessions using pre-and post-test method. The result shows a significant effect of life skill training on self-esteem and on seven domains of self-perception, that is, scholastic competence, social acceptance, athletic competence, physical appearance, job competence, behavioral conduct and global self-worth. However, no effect of training was found on the other two domains of self-perception. Results also reflect a significant effect of life skill training across the gender. The implications of the findings are discussed in the study.⁶

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

“Impact OF COMPETENCE BUILDING INTERVENTIONAL PACKAGE ON ASSERTIVE BEHAVIOUR AND SELF ESTEEM AMONG CHILDREN RESIDING IN SELECTED ORPHANAGES OF BAGALKOT DISTRICT.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the Level of life skills, Assertive behavior and self esteem among orphan children in experimental and control group.
- To determine the effectiveness of competence building interventional package on level of life skills, assertive behavior and self esteem of children in experimental group and control group.
- To find-out the association between the level of life skills with selected socio-demographic variables of orphan children of experimental group and control group.
- To find-out the association between the levels of assertive behavior and self esteem with selected socio-demographic variables of orphan children in both experimental and control group..
- To determine the correlation between life skills, assertive behavior and self esteem of orphan children in both experimental and control group.

HYPOTHESIS;

H₁: There will be significant difference in mean life skill scores among experimental and control group before and after the intervention.

H₂: There will be a significant difference in assertive behavior scores between experimental and control group of orphan children.

H₃: There will be a significant difference in self esteem scores between experimental and control group of orphan children.

H₄: There will be significant difference between the pre-test & post-test scores of life skills, assertive behavior and self esteem among orphan children in experimental group.

H₅: There will be a significant positive correlation between life skills and assertive behavior of both experimental and control group of orphan children.

H₆: There will be a significant positive correlation between life skills and self esteem of both Experimental and control group of orphan children.

H₇: There will be a significant positive correlation between assertive behavior and self esteem of both experimental and control group of orphan children.

DELIMITATIONS

The present study is delimited to

- Orphans children residing in selected orphanages of Bagalkot district.
- Orphans children between age group 10 to 18 years.
- Assessment of Life skills, assertive behavior and self esteem.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK: The present study used Ludwig von Bertalanffy's system model as its conceptual foundation.

Quasi experimental time series design

Interventional group; O₁----X₁---- O₂---- X₁---- O₃----X₁----O₅-----O₆-----O₇
 1stMonth 2ndMonth 3rdMonth

Control group: O₁-----O₂-----O₃-----O₄----O₅-----O₆

X₁=Competency building interventional package. O₁ is the observation done at the time of recruitment and O₂, O₃, O₄, post-test observations during interventional period and O₅, O₆, post-test interventional assessment done with an interval of one month by supervised sessions.

SETTING

- The present study was conducted at Balaka Bala mandir Navanagar, Bagalkot., Balika Bala mandir, Navanagar, Bagalkot, Kasturiba gandhi Balika Vidyalaya, Kadambpur, Te Taluk, Bagalkot, Vijay mahantesh Anataharam Mudhol Bagalkot district.

POPULATION

- **TARGET POPULATION:** Target population for the present study was orphan children aged between 10-18 years.
- **ACCESSIBLE POPULATION:** Accessible population in the present study was orphan children aged between 10-18 years residing at selected orphanages of Bagalkot District
- **Sample size:** 120 children
- **Experimental group:** 62 children
- **Control group:** 58 children

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SOURCE OF DATA: Data was collected from Orphan children residing in selected orphanages of Bagalkot District.

RESEARCH APPROACH: Quantitative evaluative study

RESEARCH DESIGN: Quasi experimental time series design. Pre-test post-test control group design will be used for the present study.

CRITERIA FOR SAMPLE SELECTION

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Children and adolescents aged between 10 and 18 years who are "orphans".
- Residing in selected orphanages of Bagalkot district.
- Able to understand kannada and English
- Available at the time of data collection
- willing to participate in the study

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Children who are suffering from intellectual disability and severe chronic medical illness.
- Those whose duration of stay in the home was <1 month
- Not able to co-operate during the study.
- Sick and not able to cooperate for study.
- **VARIABLES**

Variables selected for the present study are

1. INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Competence building interventional package

2. DEPENDENT VARIABLES

- Assertive behavior and self esteem of orphan children.

3. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES:

Age, Gender, Religion, Native place, Standard of studying, Duration of stay in orphanage, Parental living status (One expired, both expired), Have you attended any life skill training programme.

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

The investigator used structured interview schedule with the use of standardized structured assessment scales.

Section I: Includes items related to selected socio-demographic characteristics of orphans.

Section II: Raths assertiveness scale - will used to assess assertive behavior among orphan children .Categorization of the respondents on the basis of level of assertive behavior was done as follows: scores 121-150 very highly assertive, scores 91-120 highly assertive, scores 61-90 moderately assertive scores 31-60 less assertive and scores 0-30 verylessassertive.

Section III: Rosenberg self esteem scale - will be used to collect the data regarding self esteem of Orphan children.

RELIABILITY OF THE TOOL: Reliability was assessed between the results of first observation and retest observation by **Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient**. The calculated value ' $r = 1$ '. Suggesting the structured questionnaire to assess demographic

data was highly reliable. **Assertiveness Scale** with a Pearson r of 0.58, showing good agreement. **Rosenberg self esteem scale** a Pearson r of 0.56, showing good agreement.

PLAN FOR DATA ANALYSIS:

Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics was used for data analysis.

- Frequency, Percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation for analysis of variables.
- Independent "t" test , Paired "t" test ,The chi squared(X^2) test ,Spearman's correlation, Mann Whitney U will be used for data analysis.

PROJECTED OUTCOME

Competency interventional package is an effective means to enhance life skills among children, to encompass a range of cognitive, social, and practical abilities that are crucial for their personal growth, independence, and future success. These skills, which often overlap, are best taught through daily practice and guidance.

RESULTS

Section – I

Description of Demographic characteristics of children

To test the feasibility of intervention, homogeneity of group was assessed and effectiveness of intervention was assessed.

Table 1: Distribution of samples according to their Age and Homogeneity

N=120 (N₁ Exp group=62 N₂ Control group=58)

Present age of the child in years	Group						Chi square χ^2
	Experimental group		Control group		Total		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
10	1	1.6	2	3.44	3	2.5	$\chi^2=2.469$ P<0.246 NS
11	3	4.8	3	5.17	6	5	
12	6	9.6	9	15.5	15	12.5	
13	8	12.9	8	13.79	16	13.33	
14	11	17.7	8	13.79	19	15.83	
15	8	12.9	5	8.62	13	10.83	

16	12	19.35	12	20.58	24	20	Df=8
17	8	12.9	8	13.79	16	13.3	
18	5	8.06	3	5.17	8	6.66	
Total	62	100	58	100	120	100	

Table 2: Distribution of samples according to their gender and HomogeneityN₁=62 N₂=58

Gender	Group						Chi square
	Experimental group		Control group		Total		χ^2
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Male	18	29.03	13	22.41	31	25.83	$\chi^2=.685$ P<0.246 NS Df=1
Female	44	70.96	45	77.58	89	74.16	
Total	62	100	58	100	120	100	

Table 3 : Distribution of samples according to duration of stay in orphanage and HomogeneityN₁=62 N₂=58

Duration of stay in orphanage	Group						Chi square
	Experimental group		Control group		Total		χ^2
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Above 10 years	23	37.09	21	36.20	44	33.66	$\chi^2=.468$ P<0.246 NS Df=8
9 yrs	10	16.12	10	17.24	20	16.66	
8 yrs	13	20.96	11	18.96	24	20	
7 yrs	3	4.83	3	5.172	6	5	
6 yrs	2	3.22	2	3.44	4	3.33	
5 yrs	5	8.064	5	8.62	10	8.33	
4yrs	3	4.83	4	6.896	7	5.833	
3 yrs	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Below 2 years	3	4.83	2	3.44	5	4.16	
Total	62	100	58	100	120	100	

Table 4: Distribution of samples according to their Standard of studying and HomogeneityN₁=62 N₂=58

Standard of studying	Group						Chi square χ^2
	Experimental group		Control group		Total		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
7 th standard	3	4.83	3	5.17	6	5	$\chi^2=.471$ P<0.246 NS Df=3
8 th &9 th standard	10	16.12	12	20.68	22	18.33	
10 th standard	35	56.45	30	51.78	65	54.16	
PUC	14	22.58	13	22.14	27	22.5	
Total	62	100	58	100	120	100	

Table 5: Distribution of samples according to their Parental living status and HomogeneityN₁=62 N₂=58

Parental living status	Group						Chi square χ^2
	Experimental group		Control group		Total		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Both alive	17	27.41	16	27.58	33	27.5	$\chi^2= .117$ P<0.246 NS Df=3
Both expired	22	35.48	19	32.72	41	34.16	
One expired	23	37.096	23	39.65	46	38.33	
Total	62	100	58	100	120	100	

Section – II**Table 6 Pretest and Post test mean scores of Assertive behavior among Experimental and control group.**N₁=62 N₂=58

Self-assertive Behavior assessment	Experimental group (N ₁ =62)		Control group (N ₂ =58)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Pre-test	79.77	17.076	78.10	16.780
Post I -Test	83.77	16.524	78.07	14.661
Post II - Test	86.18	16.411	78.91	17.287
Post III - Test	89.40	15.999	78.12	16.279
Post IV- Test	92.69	15.137	78.16	16.275
Post V- Test	95.82	14.308	78.16	16.275
Post VI- Test	99.31	13.913	78.17	16.286

Table 6: Depicts the Pre test and post test mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior scores of children in both experimental and control group. The pre test mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior scores in experimental group was 79.77±17.076 and 78.10±16.780 in control group,

the post test I mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior was 83.77±16.524 where as in control group 78.07±14.661, Post test II experimental group 86.18±16.411 and control group 78.91±17.287, Post test III experimental group scores 89.40±15.999 and control group 78.12±16.279, Post test IV experimental group

scores 92.69 ± 15.137 and control group 78.16 ± 16.275 , mean and SD scores in experimental group was followed by post test V experimental group 99.31 ± 13.913 and in control group 78.17 ± 16.286 . scores 95.82 ± 14.308 and control group, Post test VI

Table 7: Pretest and Post test mean scores of Self esteem among experimental and control group.
 $N_1=62$ $N_2=58$

Self esteem Assessment	Experimental group ($N_1=62$)		Control group ($N_2=58$)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Pre-test	17.74	2.347	17.48	2.194
Post I -Test	23.21	4.066	17.48	2.194
Post II - Test	25.26	4.117	18.02	2.402
Post III - Test	27.19	4.068	17.62	2.484
Post IV- Test	29.05	3.839	17.64	2.433
Post V- Test	30.40	3.438	18.43	2.884
Post VI- Test	32.02	2.883	18.45	2.992

Table 7 : Depicts the Pre test and post test mean scores and SD of self esteem scores of children in both experimental and control group, Post test I experimental group scores 17.74 ± 2.347 and control group 17.48 ± 2.194 , Post test II experimental group scores 25.26 ± 4.117 and control group 18.02 ± 2.402 , Post test III experimental group scores $27.19 \pm$

4.068 and control group 17.62 ± 2.484 , Post test IV experimental group scores 29.05 ± 3.839 and control group 17.64 ± 2.433 , followed by post test V experimental group scores 30.40 ± 3.438 and control group 18.43 ± 2.884 , Post test VI mean and SD scores in experimental group was 32.02 ± 2.883 and in control group 18.45 ± 2.992 .

Table 8: Distribution of subjects according to their Mann-whitney, Wilcoxon w and Z scores during sequential monthly observations.
 $N_1=62$ $N_2=58$

Self esteem	Experimental group ($N_1=62$)						
	Pre test	Post test 1	Post test 2	Post test 3	Post test 4	Post test 5	Post test 6
Mann-Whitney	1686.000	418.500	258.000	96.500	46.000	36.500	10.000
Wilcoxon	3397.000	2129.500	1969.000	1807.500	1757.000	1747.500	1721.000
Z scores	-.594	-7.267	-8.113	-8.957	-9.223	-9.266	-9.414

Table 9: Distribution of children according to their level of self-esteem in pretest and post tests

Observation	Group		Self esteem					Total
			Very low	low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Pretest	Experimental	F	0	18	44	0	0	62
		%	0%	29%	71.0%	0	0	100.0%
	Control	F	0	18	40	0	0	58
		%	0%	31%	69.0%	0	0	100.0%
First post test	Experimental	F	0	3	35	23	1	62
		%	0%	4.8%	56.55%	37.1%	1.6%	100%
	Control	F	0	18	40	0	0	58

		%	0%	31.0%	69.0%	0%	0%	100%
post test 3	Experimental	F	0	0	13	46	3	62
		%	0%	0%	21%	74.2%	4.8%	100%
	Control	F	0	14	44	0	0	58
		%	0%	24.1%	75.9%	0%	0%	100%
post test 5	Experimental	F	0	0	2	31	29	62%
		%	0%	0%	3.2%	50.0%	46.8%	100%
	Control		0	12	44	2	0	58
			0%	20.7%	75.9%	3.4%	0%	100%

Table 10: Distribution of children according to their level of Assertive behavior in pretest and post tests

Observation	Group		Assertive behaviors					Total
			Very less	Less	Moderate	High	Very High	
Pretest	Experimental	F	62	0	0	0	0	62
		%	100.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	.0%	100%
	Control	F	52	6	0	0	0	58
		%	89.7%	10.3%	%	.0%	.0%	100%
First post test	Experimental	F	17	45	0	0	0	62
		%	27.4%	72.6%	.0%	.0%	.0%	100%
	Control	F	0	49	9	0	0	58
		%	.0%	84.5%	15.5%	.0%	.0%	100%
post test 3	Experimental	F	2	17	43	0	0	62
		%	3.2%	27.4%	69.4%	.0%	.0%	100%
	Control	F	0	51	7	0	0	58
		%	.0%	87.9%	12.1%	.0%	.0%	100%
post test 5	Experimental	F	2	0	23	37	0	62
		%	3.2%	.0%	37.1%	59.7%	.0%	100%
	Control		0	55	3	0	0	58
			.0%	94.8%	5.2%	.0%	.0%	100%

Table 11: Association of sociodemographic factors with self esteem and Assertive behavior of children of experimental group.

Socio Demographic Factors	Category	F	%	Self Esteem		Assertive behavior	
				Chi square /Fisher's Exact value	P value	Chi square /Fisher's Exact value	P value
Age in years	10-12	10	16.7	3.05	.55	2.3	0.68
	13-14	19	30.6				
	15-16	33	53.3				
Gender	Male	18	29	6.20	0.045*	0.849	0.65
	Female	44	71				
Religion	Hindu	52	83.9	1.8	0.93	2.4	0.87
	Muslim	7	11.3				
	Christian	2	3.2				
	Others	1	1.6				

Residence	Urban	41	66.1	2.8	0.58	6.9	0.13
	Rural	21	33.9				
Standard	5 TH	3	4.8	2.2	0.9	11.01	0.024*
	6 TH	10	16.1				
	7 TH	35	56.5				
	8 TH	14	22.6				
Parental Living status	Both alive	17	27.4	2.9	0.57	2.04	0.719
	Both Expired	22	35.5				
	Any one parent alive	23	37.1				
Training	Yes	11	17.7	3.6	1.64	5.4	0.66
	No	51	82.3				

$\alpha = 0.05$ * Significant, Abbreviation: F = Frequency, % = Percentage

DISCUSSION

Findings of the present study showed in Pre test and post test mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior scores of children in both experimental and control group. The pre test mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior scores in experimental group was 79.77 ± 17.076 and 78.10 ± 16.780 in control group, the post test I mean scores and SD of Assertive behavior was 83.77 ± 16.524 where as in control group 78.07 ± 14.661 , Post test II experimental group 86.18 ± 16.411 and control group 78.91 ± 17.287 , In this present study pre test mean scores and SD of self esteem scores in experimental group was 17.74 ± 2.347 and 14.52 ± 2.194 in control group,

The results were supported by quasi-experimental study conducted by **Tiwari, Preeti; Naik, Poonam Ramesh (2022)**. Self esteem Mean and SD scores in experimental group was 18.32 ± 2.31 and 15.62 ± 2.132 in control group.

The post test mean scores and SD of assertive behavior was 20.32 ± 3.62 where as in control group 12.14 ± 2.1341 ,

SUMMARY

Assertive behavior and self esteem is the basic core skills required for both orphans and non orphans to deal with challenges of life, it is recommended to involve these skills as a part of routine curriculum. Regular interventional sessions are needed to conduct

study on competency based education programme among orphan children. The present study proved effectiveness of training on Assertive behavior and self esteem

CONCLUSION

Children and Adolescents residing in orphanages have many psycho-social issues, in order to cope with these challenges they requires sets of skills. Training regarding development of assertive behavior and self esteem must be provided on regular basis in order to cope with life challenges. The nursing personnel were challenged to provide education and training to adolescents regarding the basic skills to cope with life competencies.

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